

CPF Technical Supplementary

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Overview

This document serves as a supplementary document for the *“Traceability of samples and data in multi-organizational environments with the Common Provenance Framework”* paper, provides the full technical specification of the Common Provenance Framework (CPF), and provides additional context and information. The document is structured as follows:

1. Section 1 defines the terms that form the terminological basis of the CPF, including a rationale for each term.
2. Section 2 defines a general non-repudiation policy for multi-organizational provenance.
3. Section 3 provides an overview and conceptualization of the CPF and its architecture.
4. Section 4 provides the specification of the Common Provenance Model (CPM), an underlying PROV-based data model for the CPF, including an extension to support non-repudiation of origin.
5. Section 5 describes a baseline algorithm for multi-organizational provenance traversal.
6. Section 6 conceptualizes three provenance exchange schemes – attached, semi-attached, and detached – for exchanging described objects together with their provenance and provenance metadata. The section compares properties of the schemes and discusses implications for the selection of a provenance appending strategy.
7. Section 7 describes the prototype implementation of the CPF Provenance Management System, a system for storing, managing, and accessing provenance in alignment with the proposed architecture and the data model. The section also summarizes how the CPF addresses the non-repudiation policy.
8. Section 8 shows an application of the CPM to a real-world multi-organizational research pipeline from digital pathology.
9. Section 9 provides technical details about how multi-organizational provenance can be incrementally built using the CPM.

1 Terms and Definitions

The following terms are defined to provide the basis for the framework, specifically addressing requirement R3: Consistent Terminology and Semantics¹.

Described object. Physical or digital object to be traced.

Described activity. Activity performed on a described object.

Provenance information. Information that documents the history of a described object and related described activities, and that contains information about the origin or source of the described object, any changes that have occurred since it was created, and who has had custody of it since it was created.²

Provenance component. Provenance information represented according to the CPM with a unique identifier assigned to it.

Finalized provenance component (FPC). Provenance component, which is prepared to be conserved or archived, and which is considered immutable.

Finalization event. An event in which provenance information is transformed into a finalized provenance component.

Meta-component. Provenance component that contains metadata about a finalized provenance component.

Provenance chain. A set of mutually interlinked finalized provenance components.

Provenance controller. A party³ that determines the purposes for which and the means by which provenance information and finalized provenance components are collected, stored, and provided, and that collects finalized provenance components documenting relevant described activities.⁴

Provenance processor. A party that performs activities related to finalized provenance components, such as generation, storage, or provision of finalized provenance components.

Provenance provider. A software, a device, a person, a subsystem, an organization, or a group that has a recognizable existence, carrying out described activities and supplying relevant provenance information.

Sender. A provenance controller that provides a described object to a provenance controller.

Receiver. A provenance controller that receives a described object from a provenance controller.

¹The requirements are formulated in the main manuscript.

²The term *provenance information* has a specific meaning in the context of the CPF as defined here.

³Party is a “natural person or legal person, whether or not incorporated, or a group of either”¹.

⁴The respective provenance controller is understood as the origin in the context of non-repudiation of origin of a finalized provenance component (see Section 2).

The cornerstone of the provenance framework is the notion of a **described object**. The definition of the described object is motivated by the presumption that traceability is a precursor for other purposes, such as quality assessment or reproducibility. In this sense, described objects are the “primary” objects for which (finalized) provenance components are collected. The definition enables the distinction of objects that are supposed to be traceable from objects that can be documented in provenance, but are not required to be traceable. For example, consider a researcher who wants to use the AI model trained in the digital pathology use case, and for that purpose, needs to evaluate how the dataset was generated during the data generation step. The dataset can be considered a described object, as it is a primary interest of the researcher. The researcher may be interested in the device used to generate the dataset, precursors (e.g., samples) used to generate it, and how these precursors were processed or acquired. For that reason, the device can be expressed in provenance information, as it affects the purpose for which the dataset can be used. However, the device is not required to be considered a described object, as it is not necessarily required to trace the full history of the device, e.g., how the device was manufactured or delivered. The interpretation of what is and what is not a described object can vary in different scenarios, depending on the purpose for which provenance information is collected. Similarly, the definition of a **described activity** enables the distinction of activities that are in the primary scope of provenance information from all activities that can potentially be documented.

The definition of **provenance information** is explicitly focused on described activities and described objects to enforce the usability of the information for the traceability purpose, as it is considered a fundamental purpose supporting other purposes. Provenance information is often captured by organizations in various forms – hospital systems, laboratory systems, (electronic) lab notebooks, device or software logs, metadata schemas, etc. – and all these forms already document the history of an object and related activities.

The term **provenance component** can be understood as a “manageable unit” of provenance information. Having such a term was motivated by the necessity to express requirements on (finalized) provenance components management, but the term provenance information is “boundless”, as it can be interpreted as “all” the information. The term provenance component does not impose any requirements or presumptions on the level of detail of the provenance information in the component, and it is up to the framework adopters to define the scope of a provenance component. Similarly, the term **meta-component** is defined to enable an expression of a manageable unit of metadata about a provenance component.

The term **finalized provenance component** is defined to distinguish all the already available provenance information, which can be formalized according to domain or scenario-dependent needs, from provenance information that is standardized within the presented framework. This enables the definition of different requirements on properties of provenance information and the management of finalized provenance components.

The terms **provenance controller**, **provenance processor**, **provenance provider**, **sender**, and **receiver** are defined to enable the distinction of different roles. Described objects pass through organizations that are provenance providers, and only these organizations perform described activities. An organization acting as a provenance provider acts as a provenance controller, or acts on behalf of a provenance controller (e.g., a provenance provider can be an organization contracted by a provenance controller to transport a sample). Consequently, provenance information is collected from provenance providers, such as devices, software, or other organizations that carry out specified activities on behalf of a provenance controller. Finalized provenance components are generated, stored, or provisioned by a provenance processor, which can be the same organization acting as a provenance controller or another organization acting on behalf of a provenance controller.

2 Non-repudiation Policy

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In this section, a general non-repudiation policy for multi-organizational provenance is defined. While addressing requirement R7: Integrity and non-repudiation, the policy is formulated as a set of requirements, with the aim to achieve non-repudiation of origin of finalized provenance components. This policy is primarily based on general requirements on irrefutable evidence² and ISO 13888³, which were adopted for provenance as part of our prior research⁴. In this context, the respective provenance controller is understood as the origin of a finalized provenance component.

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2.1 Policy requirements

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NRO-P1: FPC-controller association. Finalized provenance component shall be associated with the corresponding provenance controller.

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NRO-P2: Authenticity of FPC. Authenticity of finalized provenance component shall be verified.

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NRO-P3: Evidence-trusted party association. Only a trusted party may issue valid non-repudiation evidence for a finalized provenance component.

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NRO-P4: Authenticity of evidence. Authenticity of non-repudiation evidence shall be verifiable in long term.

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NRO-P5: Evidence-controller association. Non-repudiation evidence shall be associated with a provenance controller for which the evidence is issued.

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NRO-P6: FPC generation timestamps. Non-repudiation evidence shall contain a timestamp describing the finalization event of the associated FPC (i.e., generation of the FPC).

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NRO-P7: Evidence generation timestamps. Non-repudiation evidence shall contain a timestamp describing the non-repudiation evidence generation.

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NRO-P8: Trusted timestamps. Timestamp describing the non-repudiation evidence generation shall be generated by a trusted party.

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NRO-P9: Additional timestamps. Additional timestamps required for reconstructing past events may be included in the evidence.

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NRO-P10: Self-contained evidence. All data required to verify evidence authenticity shall be embedded in the evidence (e.g., names of used hash algorithms, digital certificates, etc.).

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NRO-P11: Primary evidence storage. Non-repudiation evidence shall be kept by the respective provenance controller or the provenance processor acting on behalf of the provenance controller.

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NRO-P12: Independent evidence storage. The provenance controller or the provenance processor shall not be the only party responsible for storing and maintaining the non-repudiation evidence.

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NRO-P13: Immutable storage. Non-repudiation evidence storage shall prevent modification of the stored content to maintain integrity.

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NRO-P14: Hardware-backed cryptography. Cryptographic operations performed by the trusted party should use secure hardware to protect private keys against disclosure.⁵

NRO-P15: Key compromise reporting window. A time period shall be defined for reporting private key compromise,⁶ and digital signatures created before expiry of this period remain valid.

3 The Architecture

3.1 Overview of the CPF

A general overview of the framework is provided in Figure 1. In the CPF, provenance is provided to the consumer by a provenance store that can be deployed in multiple instances. Provided provenance graphs include minimal traversal information, forming a provenance chain with graphs provided by other instances. The store exposes an API for keeping and retrieving provenance graphs. Once a user loads a provenance graph, they can use the traversal information to locate other components of the provenance chain, which may be stored in different instances.

Figure 1: Overall architecture of the CPF.

The framework is built around the following four layers:

- Layer 1: Existing provenance.** Provenance information that is already present in existing systems, and has any form (e.g., dedicated provenance documentation, SW logs, or metadata).
- Layer 2: Standardized provenance.** Provenance information that is represented according to the CPM and suitable for long-term storage, exchange, and automated traversal.
- Layer 3: Traversal information.** A subset of standardized provenance that can be used to traverse a distributed/multi-organizational provenance chain.
- Layer 4: Provenance metadata.** Additional extensible metadata about a provenance chain component used to manage versioning and to attach non-repudiation evidence without modifying the provenance content itself.

⁵Requiring hardware-backed cryptography may be unrealistic for some deployments. For practical implementations, this requirement may be made optional or be part of a high-assurance profile.

⁶The period is defined as the *clearance period*².

The framework supports a consistent life cycle of provenance : (i) collect provenance information in any form; (ii) transform it into a standardized CPM-compliant (finalized) provenance component; (iii) connect the components across organizational boundaries using stable identifiers resulting into a provenance chain; (iv) store and release a frozen version of the component intended for long-term preservation; (v) traverse the resulting chain to answer relevant queries; and (vi) support evolution of the chain through new versions and metadata updates, without rewriting previously released components.

PROV-DM was chosen as the underlying data model for the standardized provenance information representation, as it provides a solid foundation for harmonizing provenance from heterogeneous systems into a common structure and is naturally compatible with traversal and querying. PROV-DM is also widely recognized across different domains⁵⁻⁷. In multi-organizational environments, the most critical interoperability issue is the ability to traverse across organizational boundaries reliably. For that reason, the framework prescribes a common structure for traversing a provenance chain, which is independent of domain semantics, enabling a generic traversal algorithm.

An additional benefit of separating the traversal information from potentially highly granular domain-dependent details is that it aligns with the least privilege principle⁸, as it enables provenance chain traversal without exposing unnecessary content. It also reduces coupling between domain ontologies and cross-organizational traversal logic.

Long-term usability of a provenance chain requires integrity, which is achieved primarily by a versioning mechanism and related provenance metadata. Provenance metadata are kept externally to the provenance pieces, which supports immutable releases and allows different profiles without changing the core metadata representation.

3.2 Conceptualization of the CPF

This section describes how the framework works in terms of the life cycle of finalized provenance components.

3.2.1 FPC generation

As provenance information is currently collected in various forms, the framework suggests the transformation of provenance information into finalized provenance components to enable syntactic and semantic interoperability of the information and to enable its processing, while *traversal* through provenance information was identified as a foundation for any kind of processing (e.g., quality assessment of described objects). The transformation occurs during a finalization event. It is up to adopters of the framework to decide when the finalization event occurs. Generally speaking, it can happen upon completion of the respective described activity (e.g., when a dataset is generated or an AI model trained), on request (e.g., when someone requests the resulting described object), or periodically (e.g., long-term storage of biological material, when any sample-related event may not occur for months or years).

Finalized provenance components may be generated in two distinct ways. The first option, as depicted in Figure 2, is to use available (potentially proprietary and legacy) provenance information to generate a finalized provenance component directly.

As an alternative, provenance information can be translated first into a provenance component, which is subsequently transformed into a finalized provenance component, as depicted in Figure 3. The potential benefit of this alternative approach is that provenance components are easier to generate, as they do not necessarily contain all the information required for long-term storage of the components (e.g., links to other finalized provenance

Figure 2: Schema of transformation of provenance information into a finalized provenance component. IS stands for Information System.

components). For this reason, provenance providers can generate provenance components that are pre-prepared for the finalization event in a way that they will contain the available information and a template structure for the missing information. A provenance processor can benefit from this simplification, as its task would be to feed in the missing information. At the same time, providing the missing information immediately by the respective provenance providers (e.g., biobank automation devices or freezers) may not always be realistic, as these providers are typically presumed to not know the rest of the respective provenance chain.

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Figure 3: Schema of transformation of provenance information into a provenance component before it is transformed into a finalized provenance component.

3.2.2 FPC interlinking

If a described activity of one provenance controller (a sender) is followed by a described activity of another provenance controller (a receiver), where the latter uses the output of the former as input, both provenance controllers can produce two separate finalized provenance components connected to each other forming a provenance chain. By applying this process throughout the life cycle of a described object, an uninterrupted documentation of the whole life cycle of a described object can be established, with each finalized provenance component managed independently by distinct organizations. Connections between components can be established in both backward and forward directions. This is depicted in Figure 4.

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Figure 4: Schema of a provenance chain composed of finalized provenance components.

In the CPF, backward links are mandatory, and forward links are optional. The reason is that the forward link creation requires that the sender of a described object is notified about the new component created by the receiver,⁷ and that the sender's finalized provenance component is updated accordingly to include the forward link.

To enable the connection between components, each finalized provenance component and meta-component shall be assigned a unique resolvable identifier that can be used to access the corresponding components' content, while access to the content will be restricted to authenticated and authorized users where applicable. Global uniqueness and long-term persistency of identifiers can be achieved in practice by so-called persistent identifiers (PIDs)¹⁰. A PID is registered by an organization, which manages the PIDs in the long term. Each PID is mapped to the actual location (URI), where the identified object (e.g., a finalized provenance component) is accessible. In practice, schemes based on Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)⁸ or Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC)⁹ can be used.

3.2.3 FPC provision

Once a finalized provenance component is generated, it becomes available to authorized users and remains immutable with the assigned identifier. For that reason, the versioning of the component is performed outside the provenance component by creating a new finalized provenance component that incorporates additional, reduced, or updated information. The new component is then perceived as a new version and a replacement of the original provenance component.

The immutability property ensures that the finalized components' versioning mechanism does not break potential hashes or digital signatures, which can be used for verifying the components' integrity, authenticity, or non-repudiation.

3.3 CPF Architecture

This section defines a uniform SOA-based architecture for the CPF that enables addressing the general requirements R1–R8 (presented in the main manuscript) and the requirements

⁷This mechanism is also known as provenance pingback⁹.

⁸<https://www.doi.org/>

⁹<https://www.pidconsortium.net/>

of the non-repudiation policy presented in Section 2.

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3.3.1 The architecture

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To address R1: Architecture for multi-organizational provenance, the following SOA-based architecture is defined. The architecture consists of the following components, which can be deployed in multiple instances. Figure 5 shows the components of the architecture and their interactions.

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1. **FPC Store Component** is a service that provides basic functionality related to the storage, retrieval, and versioning of FPCs.
2. **Authentication and Authorization Component** is a service that provides functionality related to the authentication and authorization of users.
3. **ID Generator Component** is a service for generating identifiers that are assigned to FPCs, and are later used to access the FPCs' content.
4. **Traversal Component** is a service that provides advanced traversal and lookup functions. The Traversal Component operates primarily on top of the FPC Store Components.
5. **Validator Component** is a service that provides validation functions, such as semantic or syntactic validation of FPCs.

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Optionally, the architecture can be extended with the following components required to achieve non-repudiation:

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1. **Trusted Party** is a service that provides functionality to support non-repudiation of stored FPCs, such as non-repudiation evidence handling.
2. **Certification Authority** is a service that issues digital certificates to verify the identity of a user or an organization.
3. **Timestamping Authority** is a service that provides functionality related to trusted timestamps¹¹.

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Storing an FPC. Storing an FPC is performed as follows.

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1. Presume that a user possesses a provenance component that is prepared to be finalized.
2. Optionally, a user or an organization the user is acting on behalf of is assigned a digital certificate, which can be used to verify the user's or organization's identity by verifying digital signatures associated with that certificate.
3. The user is authenticated by the Authentication and Authorization Component, and is provided with an authentication token uniquely assigned to the user. The token can be used for authorization by other components.
4. The user requests the ID Generator Component to generate a globally unique identifier for the component.

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Figure 5: Components of the CPF architecture and their interactions. Optional components related to non-repudiation are drawn in dashed squares.

5. The user finalizes the component, i.e., mainly assigns the generated component ID to the component. Optionally, the user can digitally sign the document and request the Timestamping Authority (or the Trusted Party) to provide a timestamp for this operation. 314
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6. The user requests the FPC Store Component to store the component. The FPC Store authorizes the user using the Authentication and Authorization Component and checks the validity of the FPC using the Validator Component. 317
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7. Optionally, the Store Component uses the Trusted Party to verify the digital signature of the FPC and to generate the non-repudiation evidence. The signed evidence, together with the respective public key, is stored by the Trusted Party and returned to the FPC Store. 320
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8. If the checks are successful, the FPC is stored by the FPC Store. 324

As finalized provenance components are implemented as PROV bundles, the assignment of the identifier to the component is technically realized by specifying the respective bundle ID. In PROV, these identifiers have the form of a qualified name, i.e., a prefix concatenated with a local part. The prefix is mapped to a namespace, which is a URI. The namespace, when concatenated with the local part, is also a URI. Global uniqueness of the ID can then be achieved by using a namespace that uniquely identifies the organization. Uniqueness of the local part can be achieved by the controller or an authority. 325
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It is presumed that different organizations will use their own instances of the FPC Store Component. For smaller organizations, it may not be feasible to deploy and maintain their own instance. In such cases, external service providers or authorities may operate FPC Store instances. The same holds for the Trusted Party, which cannot be operated by the provenance controller. 332
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Querying provenance chain. Once a finalized provenance component is stored, a user can request it directly from the FPC Store by resolving the component identifier to the actual web location where the component is stored, and sending a request to that location. Alternatively, the user can run a query over the Traversal Component. It is presumed that the FPC identifier is always known to the user.

4 The Common Provenance Model

The Common Provenance Model (CPM)^{12,13} is the underlying data model of the CPF. The main goal of the model is to enhance interoperability of finalized provenance components, providing better support for a unified traversal mechanism, regardless of the particular processes or objects documented by the provenance. The CPM is an extension of PROV-DM¹⁴, which represents provenance information as a directed graph with semantically annotated nodes and edges. The nodes represent entities, activities, or agents, and the edges represent their mutual relations. The CPM specializes the PROV-DM types (i.e., PROV entities, PROV activities, and PROV agents) and defines constraints on how these shall be used in conformance to the context defined by the CPF. The CPM types and attributes are listed in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Keywords SHALL, SHOULD, and MAY in this section shall be interpreted as defined in RFC 2119¹⁵.

4.1 CPM Types and Attributes

Table 1: The table lists core elements of the CPM and their mandatory attributes in a finalized provenance component. The `cpm` prefix stands for the CPM namespace (<https://www.commonprovenancemodel.org/>, where the model will be sustained.)

CPM Type	Type description	Attributes
Backward connector	A connector* that represents a received described object	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: (a mandatory attribute; <code>cpm:backwardConnector</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute) - <code>cpm:referencedBundleId</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedMetaBundleId</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedBundleSpecV</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedmetaBundleSpecV</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedBundleHashValue</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:hashAlg</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:provenanceServiceUri</code>: an optional attribute
Forward connector	A connector* that represents a described object that can be or has been sent from a sender to a receiver	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; (<code>cpm:forwardConnector</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute)
Forward connector specialized	A connector* that represents a described object that has been sent from a sender to a receiver	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; (<code>cpm:forwardConnectorSpec</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute) - <code>cpm:referencedBundleId</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedMetaBundleId</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedBundleSpecV</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedmetaBundleSpecV</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:provenanceServiceUri</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:hashAlg</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedBundleHashValue</code>: a mandatory attribute
Identifier entity	A provenance structure that represents an external identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; <code>cpm:id</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute - <code>cpm:externalId</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:externalIdType</code>: a mandatory attribute
Main activity	A provenance structure that represents the described activity documented in a particular provenance component	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; <code>cpm:mainActivity</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute - <code>cpm:referencedMetaBundleId</code>: mandatory attribute - <code>cpm:referencedmetaBundleSpecV</code>: a mandatory attribute - <code>dct:hasPart</code>: an optional attribute
Sender agent	A provenance structure that represents a sender in the context of passing a described object between two provenance controllers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; <code>cpm:senderAgent</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute
Receiver agent	A provenance structure that represents a receiver in the context of passing a described object between two provenance controllers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; <code>cpm:receiverAgent</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute
Current agent	A provenance structure that represents a provenance controller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>prov:type</code>: a mandatory attribute; <code>cpm:currentAgent</code> is a mandatory value for this attribute

* A *connector* serves as an interconnection between provenance components and represents a described object which can be or has been exchanged between a sender and a receiver.

Table 2: The table lists attributes used in the CPM.

CPM Attribute	Attribute description
<code>cpm:externalId</code>	External identifier of a described object or a described activity, which is represented by a PROV entity, PROV activity or PROV agent.
<code>cpm:externalIdType</code>	Type of the external identifier.
<code>cpm:hasId</code>	An indication whether the PROV entity having this attribute has an external identifier expressed as a standalone entity.
<code>cpm:describedObjectType</code>	Type of the object represented by the PROV entity.
<code>cpm:referencedBundleId</code>	Identifier of a PROV bundle referenced by the connector that contains this attribute.
<code>cpm:referencedMetaBundleId</code>	Identifier of a PROV bundle that contains respective provenance component's metadata in the standardized representation.
<code>cpm:referencedBundleSpecV</code>	Identification of the CPM version to which the referenced bundle conforms.
<code>cpm:referencedMetaBundleSpecV</code>	Identification of the CPM version to which the referenced meta-bundle conforms.
<code>cpm:provenanceServiceUri</code>	URI of a service where a provenance component can be requested using its identifier.
<code>cpm:hashValue</code>	A hash value of a described object, which is represented by the PROV entity, presuming that the described object is a digital object and not a physical object.
<code>cpm:referencedBundleHashValue</code>	A hash value of a PROV bundle referenced by the connector in which the attribute is present.
<code>cpm:hashAlg</code>	Algorithm used to create a hashValue.
<code>cpm:contactIdPid</code>	A resolvable persistent identifier dereferencing to actual contact information (e.g., email address) that can be used to contact a person or organization represented by a particular agent. The value of this attribute is a persistent identifier, thus it has the form of a qualified name.

4.2 Provenance Components

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The CPF distinguishes a provenance component as a manageable unit of provenance information, which can also be considered an intermediate step in transforming provenance information into a finalized provenance component. Each provenance component shall contain a provenance graph designed according to PROV-DM¹⁴. This graph shall be encapsulated in a PROV bundle¹⁶ that is assigned a unique identifier, and shall be valid according to the validation procedure defined in the PROV-CONSTRAINTS¹⁷ document.

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As the primary purpose of collecting finalized provenance components is to enable traceability of described objects and related information, special attention is given to mechanisms for identifying described objects in provenance components. In fact, PROV does not stipulate any specific mechanism for identifying described objects, so that adopters of the standard may determine their own way, potentially hindering interoperability of provenance from different sources. According to the CPM, a described object shall be expressed in a provenance component as a PROV entity, and its identifier shall be associated with that entity using one

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of the following two mechanisms.

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1. Using the `cpm:externalId` attribute. The value of this attribute is the identifier of the described object, and no additional information is associated with this identifier. 371
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2. Using the `cpm:hasId` attribute for a PROV entity representing a described object and an alternate PROV entity of type `cpm:id` representing the identifier. The pattern is shown in Figure 6. This mechanism allows for attachment of additional information related to the identifier, such as identifier type (analogous to `Content-Type` in email headers). Using the type and the identifier (or potentially other optional attributes), an application processing such a PROV entity can determine means to access the referenced object in cases when this is enabled. This way, harmonized means to refer from a provenance component to an external system is enabled. 373
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Figure 6: A pattern for the expression of identifiers with additional information.

Each described object can have multiple identifiers, but the mechanisms used to express the identifier should not be combined with a single described object in a provenance component. The identifier property of a PROV entity should not be used to express the identifier of the described object, as the requirements on handling internal provenance structure identifiers may differ from the requirements on the identification of described objects. The only exception is an entity representing a finalized provenance component in a meta-component. 381
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4.3 Finalized Provenance Components

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Each finalized component consists of two types of information: 1) traversal information that is used for navigation and traversal of a provenance chain; and 2) domain- or scenario-specific information documenting described activities, which may correspond to a provenance component to which the traversal information is properly attached. A simplified schema of a provenance chain with the traversal and domain-specific information is depicted in Figure 7. 388
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Figure 7: Simplified schema of a provenance chain with references to provenance information.

4.3.1 Traversal Information – Basic Structure

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The general structure of the traversal information is depicted in Figure 8. The core idea is to separate the low-granularity traversal information, and to prescribe its mandatory structure. The idea requires the resulting provenance graph to contain a sub-graph with a strictly prescribed structure of derivation paths between graph nodes (PROV entities) that represent traceable inputs (backward connectors) and traceable outputs (forward connectors) of a documented process (main activity).

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Each finalized provenance component shall contain exactly one main activity that should generate at least one forward connector. The forward connectors represent outputs of the described activity that can be subsequently used by a receiver, and serve as a means to connect subsequent finalized provenance components to the chain. The connection between the components is realized by including a PROV entity — the connector — with the same identifier in the receiver’s finalized provenance component. The mandatory attributes associated with the backward connector provide the link to the sender’s finalized provenance component, as specified in Table 1. The mechanism is depicted in Figure 9.

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Figure 8: General structure of the traversal information in a provenance component.

Figure 9: A schema of the interconnection between two provenance components with the support for backward traceability.

This way, the backward traceability of a described object is enabled without the necessity of updating the sender's finalized provenance component. A finalized provenance component without a backward connector represents the beginning of a provenance chain (e.g., sample acquisition), as there is no *traceable* input to represent.

To enable the forward traceability of described objects, the forward link is included in the sender's component. The forward traceability is realized by adding a specialized forward connector entity that specializes the "general" forward connector. The attributes associated

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with the specializing entity provide the link to the receiver's finalized provenance component and the respective meta-component. The mechanism is depicted in Figure 10. 415

Using this mechanism is not mandatory, as the attribute values of the specialized forward connector may not be known to the sender at the time of the sender's finalization event, and neither later. An example of this situation is when a sender makes an open dataset available together with the respective finalized provenance component and does not know who will use or has used the dataset (e.g., as the Camelyon dataset¹⁸). In such a scenario, receivers can use the dataset, generate a corresponding finalized provenance component, and connect it to the existing forward connector to enable backward traceability. 416
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Figure 10: A schema of the interconnection between two provenance components with the support for both backward and forward traceability.

The actual link between a finalized provenance component and its metadata is realized using the `cpm:referencedMetaBundleId` attribute present in the backward connector and the main activity. 424
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The CPM presumes that all the information necessary to create the links between finalized provenance components (component's id, meta-component's id, connector's id, etc.) are exchanged between organizations as part of their communication protocol. No other provenance structures (types of nodes), except the types presented in this section, are allowed in the traversal information. 427
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Figure 12: Connection of domain-specific part (red box) to the traversal information solely using the `prov:specializationOf` relation.

does not necessarily need access to highly granular domain-specific descriptions. Such a query can be resolved using only the traversal information.

This approach is aligned with common mechanisms for provenance access control — transformation of a provenance graph into a valid and consistent view appropriate for an authorized user — the transformation algorithm may just *cut off* the domain-specific part by removing `prov:specializationOf` relations through which it is connected to the traversal information. This transformation will leave the resulting graphs valid according to PROV-CONSTRAINTS¹⁷, as both the traversal information and the domain-specific part remain intact by the removal. This can be proven by showing that removing the `prov:specializationOf` relations will preserve all the constraints defined in the PROV-CONSTRAINTS document¹⁷.

4.4 Meta-component

As finalized provenance components are considered immutable, a versioning mechanism is necessary to create a new version of a finalized provenance component while sustaining the integrity of the respective provenance chain. The versioning mechanism may be required, for instance, to correct wrong information (potential errors are described in²⁰ or²¹) or to add missing information (e.g., specialized forward connectors for forward traceability). The CPF defines a versioning mechanism for finalized provenance components, and the CPM supports it by defining a data model for representing versioning information in a meta-component (partially addressing R4: Provenance interoperability).

The mandatory representation of how multiple versions of a provenance component are documented in a meta-component is depicted in Figure 13. The component is represented by a general entity expressing general attributes, and a specialized entity expressing at-

tributes specific to a particular version of that provenance component. In the case of multiple versions of the same component, they are all expressed in the meta-component as specializations of the general entity, and related via the PROV revision relation. This mechanism is based on the revision pattern¹⁹, and loosely follows the semantics defined in the PAV ontology²².

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Figure 13: A schema of the versioning information in a meta-component.

The actual link from meta-component to the respective provenance component is established by the identifier of a PROV entity representing the specific version of the provenance component. Because the identifier is resolvable to its content, it can be used to access the component's content.

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The proposed structure of the versioning information can be understood as the foundation to which any additional information can be attached. This may include hashes or digital signatures of the components, or information about when the component was created. The proposed approach supports modular attachment of additional required functionality, which can be the subject of a standalone standard or specification.

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4.4.1 Extending meta-component to support non-repudiation

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To address requirements R4: Interoperability, R7: Integrity and non-repudiation, and the requirements present in the non-repudiation policy (Section 2), meta-components can include non-repudiation evidence. Figure 14 shows how the versioning information in a meta-component can be extended for that purpose.

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Non-repudiation evidence can be represented as:

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1. A PROV entity representing the issued non-repudiation evidence. The entity contains required attributes, such as a digital signature of the rest of the evidence, identifier of the responsible provenance controller, respective finalized provenance component identifier and creation time, hash values, used algorithms, or certificate of the trusted party used to sign the evidence.
2. A PROV agent representing a trusted party that issued the evidence, including the party identifier.

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Figure 14: Example of a representation of non-repudiation evidence (dotted box) which is attached to the versioning information in a meta-component (dashed box).

3. A PROV activity representing the evidence issue, containing the evidence issue date and time.

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5 Provenance Chain Traversal Algorithm

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Once available, a provenance chain can be traversed to look up information sources and origins of a described object. This section describes a baseline algorithm for traversing provenance chains.

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Presume the existence of a described object (e.g., the WSI dataset in the digital pathology use case) that is documented by a provenance chain, and that there is a user (e.g., a researcher) who would like to assess the quality of the described object for their particular study (where the dataset is to be used to train AI models). To enable the researcher to find the respective information in a provenance chain, the researcher is provided with the identifier of a finalized provenance component documenting the described activity that produced the described object, and with the identifier of the forward connector representing the described object in that provenance component. With these identifiers, the user can ask various queries about the history of the described object using the corresponding provenance chain. Depending on the specific situation, the query can be resolved either by providing information just from the traversal information (e.g., get connector identifiers and component identifiers of all the documented precursors in the chain) or the domain-specific part of the provenance chain (depending on what specific information is present in the domain-specific part).

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With no regard to what specific kind of query is run, the underlying algorithm must be able to 1) traverse the traversal information of the provenance chain components, and 2) iden-

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tify the information required to answer the query in a particular component. An underlying algorithm for traversing the traversal information can perform as follows: 535
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1. The algorithm takes at least two parameters as input: 537
 - (a) A forward connector ID. The connector represents the described object that is the subject of the query.¹⁰ 538
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 - (b) A finalized provenance component ID, where the traversal starts. 540
2. The component is accessed using its identifier (which is resolvable to the component's content, as required by the CPF), the component content is checked, and the type of the input connector is verified. 541
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3. If the type is not correct, report an error. 544
4. If the type is correct, then perform the traversal: 545
 - (a) Find all the backward connectors from which the input forward connector is derived using the derivation relation between the forward and backward connectors (or possibly using the redundant connectors). 546
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 - (b) For each backward connector found, run the algorithm using the backward connector identifier and the referenced bundle identifier present in the backward connector's attributes. This can be performed either in a recursive/non-recursive or federated/non-federated way, having an impact on who can see the response.¹¹ 549
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5. Terminate when no new derived backward connectors are found. 553

The confidentiality of information stored in a provenance chain is ensured by proper authorization, which is part of accessing the component's content. As a result, the traversal algorithm is provided only with finalized provenance components and their parts for which the respective user is authorized. 554
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The algorithm always terminates, as provenance chains are finite, and a cycle is never present in a provenance chain because derivation relations over connectors represent a temporal ordering, and the CPM template for traversal information prohibits deriving a connector from itself (directly or indirectly). The algorithm can be run in the "forward" direction analogously using the forward connectors. 558
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Depending on what information is important to answer the query, the underlying algorithm can exploit additional information present in finalized provenance components or respective meta-components, for instance: 563
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- The query may require running the algorithm on the latest versions of finalized provenance components (a component version linked by a connector is not necessarily the latest one). In such a case, before loading the linked component, the algorithm can use the referenced meta-component identifier specified in the connector or the main activity of the referenced component to find the latest version of that component. 566
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- The query may require looking into meta-components for other reasons than checking the versions. For instance, meta-components can contain information such as digital signatures, hashes, or certificates (as exemplified in Section 4.4.1). 571
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¹⁰Alternatively, the identifier of a described object to be traced may be used, presuming that this is linkable to a backward or forward connector.

¹¹A detailed analysis of possible situations is provided in²³.

- The query may require looking into the domain-specific information. To do so, it may be suitable to store some kind of a tag or indicator in the traversal part of a finalized provenance component that would indicate the presence of some information in the domain-specific part of that component. For instance, if the query requires information about a sample acquisition, the underlying algorithm can specifically look for a main activity of type `OBI_0000659`¹², a code referring to a specimen collection process. It is the purpose of domain- and scenario-specific adoptions of the CPM to define such extensions to support domain- and scenario-specific queries. In the worst-case scenario, if there were no such indicators in the traversal information, the algorithm can always traverse the domain-specific part of each finalized provenance component (which is unnecessarily complex and time- and resource-consuming).

6 Provenance Exchange Schemes

If a described object is modified, corresponding new information can be added to the respective provenance chain, and the metadata of the finalized provenance component must be updated accordingly. The CPF provides two strategies for appending new information:

1. by addition of a new finalized provenance component to a provenance chain;
2. by adding a new version of a finalized provenance component into a provenance chain.

Intuitively, if a described object is modified and a new version is obtained, the versioning mechanism can be applied. On the other hand, if an object is modified and a new object is obtained as a result, then a new provenance component can be appended to the provenance chain. However, determining when an object can be considered a new version or a new object is not always straightforward²⁴. Additionally, each appending strategy has implications on how respective provenance component metadata is handled in a multi-organizational environment, and implementing these implications may not always be feasible. Being familiar with these implications is essential to making informed decisions when adopting the framework.

For that reason, this work introduces and describes Provenance Exchange Schemes — a novel categorization of options for exchanging described objects, their provenance (e.g., a finalized provenance component), and provenance metadata (e.g., respective meta-component) between organizations. Subsequently, using the exchange schemes, situations in which one appending strategy can be preferred over the others are discussed. These results were taken into account when designing the CPM, which addresses requirement R2: Multi-organizational retrieval. In this section, the term provenance is again used in a general sense (not as defined in the CPF terminology), because the introduced concepts apply in general, not just in the CPF.

6.1 Provenance Exchange Schemes

The categorization of how provenance and provenance metadata can be handled with regard to exchanged objects is described using the following three provenance exchange schemes: attached, semi-attached, and detached (Figure 15).

¹²http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000659

Figure 15: Illustration of the provenance exchange schemes: a) the attached scheme, where the provenance and its metadata are not embedded within the exchanged object; b) the attached scheme, where the provenance and its metadata are embedded within the exchanged object; c) the semi-attached scheme with a reference to provenance metadata; d) the semi-attached scheme with a reference to provenance; e) the detached scheme where both provenance and provenance metadata are referenced. The lines between squares express correspondence.

6.1.1 Attached Scheme

In the attached scheme, provenance and provenance metadata are part of the communication between organizations. In particular, when the object is exchanged between organizations, the copy of the corresponding provenance and its metadata are also exchanged. This may be done either by providing it as a standalone piece of information outside the object (Figure 15 (a)), or by embedding the information directly in the described object (Figure 15 (b)). As a result, when the process of the object exchange is finished, the receiver has an actual copy of the provenance and its metadata. For instance, an RO-Crate carrying data with provenance, or data formats that include provenance in their header, fall within this category.

6.1.2 Semi-attached Schemes

In the semi-attached scheme, either provenance or provenance metadata is not part of the communication between organizations (only one is present). As a consequence, the receiver of the object must make an additional request to get a copy of the missing part after the object exchange is finished. For instance, an RO-Crate that encapsulates data with a reference to its provenance stored externally falls within the semi-attached scheme.

1. **Semi-attached scheme with provenance attached:** provenance is part of the communication between a sender and a receiver, but the corresponding metadata is not part of the communication (Figure 15 (c)).
2. **Semi-attached scheme with metadata attached:** metadata of provenance is part of the communication between a sender and a receiver, but provenance is not part of the communication (Figure 15 (d)).

6.1.3 Detached Scheme

In the detached scheme, neither provenance nor metadata of provenance are part of the communication between organizations (Figure 15 (e)). As a consequence, the receiver of the object must make additional requests to obtain copies of both the provenance and the metadata after the object exchange is finished. For instance, an RO-Crate that encapsulates data with a reference to its provenance and the metadata stored externally to the object falls within the detached scheme (see²⁵ for further details on possible configurations of byte sequences and metadata references in FAIR Digital Objects).

6.2 Properties of the Schemes

The available literature presents various properties of provenance coupling schemes^{26,27}, which is a categorization of how provenance is coupled with described objects while they are stored. In contrast, provenance exchange schemes presented in this work focus on how provenance (and its metadata) is coupled with described objects when they are exchanged. Various properties of provenance coupling schemes are adopted, amended, and described in the context of the provenance exchange schemes in Table 3.

Additionally, some properties that were studied in the context of provenance coupling schemes are not influenced by selecting any of the exchange schemes. These include availability²⁸, consistency^{29,30}, integrity, and non-repudiation (trustworthiness³⁰). Availability is related to the storage and preservation of information, not to the exchange. Each of consistency, integrity, and non-repudiation requires verification of some information (e.g., a hash, a digital signature, or a trusted timestamp) with respect to the received provenance

and its metadata. Presuming that all the information is interoperable, available, and accessible to the receiver, these properties are not affected by the selection of any of the exchange schemes.

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Table 3: The table compares properties of provenance and its metadata in the context of the attached, semi-attached, and the detached scheme. The text in the table should be interpreted in the following way: is the property on the given row affected by the selection of an exchange scheme between a sender and a receiver? The properties are described solely in the context of the exchange of the information between a sender and a receiver, not in the context of their subsequent storage by the receiver or potential subsequent receivers. The referenced properties (e.g., “Access control”) were presented in an existing work. The unreferenced properties (e.g., “Accessibility”) are introduced here.

Property of provenance and provenance metadata in a scheme*	Attached scheme	Semi-attached and detached schemes
Accessibility	As the actual copy of provenance and its metadata are provided together with the exchanged object, the scheme is less prone to accessibility errors in comparison with the semi-attached and detached schemes. The reason is that no additional request is needed to get the actual copies.	As the actual copy of provenance or its metadata** is not immediately provided to the receiver after the exchange of the object is finished, the scheme is more prone to accessibility errors than the attached scheme. The reason is that there is a need to make an additional request to get the actual copies.
Confidentiality (by access control ³⁰ and encryption ^{***})	The attached scheme requires that authorization decision related to provenance and its metadata is made when accessing the exchanged object, as they are provided to a receiver together. Encryption can be used to protect confidential information in the attached scheme, but this would introduce additional complexity related to encryption/decryption keys management and pose additional risks related to keys leakage or keys/scheme deprecation.	The semi-attached and the detached scheme separate the moment of making the authorization decision (especially in the case of the separation of access control strategies for exchanged objects and provenance), as the object, provenance, and its metadata are exchanged between a sender and a receiver at different time instances.
Interoperability	Interoperability should not be affected by the determination of the exchange scheme, as the provenance and its metadata must be interoperable in every scheme so that the receiver can use it. However, the schemes differ in how the interoperability is achieved. If provenance and its metadata is expressed in a standardized way, the receiver can access it directly. Otherwise, the receiver must use an appropriate tool that transforms the received information into an intelligible representation.	Interoperability should not be affected by the determination of the exchange scheme, as the provenance and its metadata must be interoperable in every scheme so that the receiver can use it. The transformation into the standardized representation may be realized by an API, through which the receiver requests provenance or its metadata, or must translate the result using an appropriate tool.
Size & Ease of Distribution	Since provenance and its metadata may be relatively large, their inclusion inside the communication between a sender and a receiver may negatively affect the ease of their distribution.	Providing provenance or its metadata in a response to a separate request may ease their distribution.

Performance and scalability properties ³⁰ of queries over provenance	Performance of queries over attached provenance and its metadata can be better, as the information is always already directly accessible to the user.	Detaching the information can cause degradation of query performance in case the queries run over “remote” information.
Physical objects	Provenance and its metadata can not be part of physical objects, such as biological samples. For the description of physical objects, an attached scheme with the provenance and its metadata outside the object, a semi-attached scheme, or the detached scheme can be applied.	The detached scheme can be used for the description of physical objects.

* Particular scheme has no effect on its feasibility in distributed & heterogeneous environments^{27,28}, as the “distributed” property is fulfilled per se by the fact that the object, its provenance and provenance metadata are exchanged between a sender and a receiver. Availability is not affected by the selection of an exchange scheme, as it is related to the storage and preserving of information, not to the exchange. Each of the Consistency^{29,30}, Integrity, and Non-repudiation (Trustworthiness³⁰) properties require verification of some information (e.g., hash, digital signature, trusted timestamp, or other evidence) with respect to received provenance and its metadata. Presuming that all the information is interoperable, available and accessible for the receiver, achieving these properties is not affected by the selection of an exchange scheme.

** Depending on which one is not included in the communication between a sender and a receiver. This applies to each “provenance or its metadata” phrase occurrence in this table.

*** Access control and encryption² are common ways of achieving confidentiality of information.

6.3 Implications

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Once the exchanged object, its provenance, and provenance metadata or references to them are received and processed by a receiver, the receiver may decide where the respective provenance record (i.e., finalized provenance component in the CPF) documenting its described activity will be stored, and which appending strategy will be used.

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In the attached scheme, the two general appending strategies, i.e., versioning or adding provenance pieces to the provenance chain, do not differ significantly. If an object and related metadata are meant to “travel together” (e.g., as part of the data file header), then a receiver of the object can append it directly, with no regard to which of the two appending strategies is used. On the other hand, if any of the information is referenced in a semi-attached or detached scheme, the properties of the two appending strategies can vary. If a new version is created in the chain, the receiver must be authorized to append the versioning information. On the other hand, if the receiver adds a new provenance piece to the provenance chain, the receiver is not necessarily bound to use any specific metadata of the provenance piece.

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One of the most important questions is whether a receiver of an object should even be able to create a new version of an existing provenance record that was created by another organization. Since a provenance piece documents part of an object’s life cycle when a particular organization handled it, we suggest that this documentation should not be updated by another organization, and suggest enabling the creation of new versions by different organizations (different from the organization that originally created the finalized provenance component) only in justified cases, e.g., when an organization ceases to exist and an error in provenance is detected later. In this situation, it would be beneficial if another organization, e.g., an authority, could create a corrected version. As a result, the versioning mechanism should not be used to append new information to a chain without additional integrity assurances when an object crosses organizational boundaries. The assurance must guarantee that the new version only appended new content, and that the original provenance content was not modified.

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Another aspect that affects the determination of the appending strategy is the formats of the exchanged objects. For instance, genomic data and their metadata are part of the MPEG-G standard³¹, which currently covers documentation of steps ranging from raw sequence reads to their alignment to a reference sequence. Each time a new dataset is derived from an MPEG-G file (e.g., a raw genomic dataset stored as an MPEG-G file, and another dataset with aligned reads will be derived from that raw genomic dataset), the derived dataset is expected to be represented as a new MPEG-G file. In this scenario, the new file is a new object that can be documented intuitively in a new piece of provenance chain.

The determination of the provenance appending strategy might also be affected by the assignment of identifiers for exchanged described objects. For example, Zenodo¹³, an open repository for storing digital research objects, distinguishes identifiers for the objects themselves and for their specific versions. Using such identifiers for the objects might indicate situations where appending a new provenance piece is more appropriate over the provenance versioning mechanism (or vice versa). In particular, when a derived object is assigned the new object identifier, creating a new provenance piece in a chain intuitively seems to be the preferred option. On the contrary, if the described object is assigned an identifier of a new version of another existing object, creating a new version of a provenance piece may be the preferred option.

6.4 Further Notes

An important aspect to consider when adopting a provenance solution is determining an appropriate provenance exchange method. This work describes the general properties of the provenance exchange schemes. However, the properties of the resulting provenance chain are determined by the combination of all provenance exchange schemes between different organizations in a chain and the application of provenance coupling schemes for provenance storage within each organization. For example, if the entire workflow adopts the attached provenance exchange scheme and tight coupling^{26,27} of the object with provenance — e.g., all the provenance and described object is present in an exchanged RO-Crate, which is iteratively appended — each consecutive organization will have access to it. On the other hand, if a detached scheme is used for a single segment of the workflow, an authorized receiver can access related provenance via a reference and redistribute it independently, providing access to other organizations in the chain, similarly to the attached scheme. This bottleneck cannot be simply avoided through architectural decisions but must be addressed, e.g., through contractual agreements between the organizations involved in distributed provenance handling.

In the case of the detached scheme, neither the standardized provenance nor its metadata is part of the communication between a sender and a receiver. In this scheme, how references to the respective provenance component and meta-component are designed and represented is within the constituency of the exchanged information format or communication protocol between a sender and a receiver. The method for referencing provenance components using the connectors and the main activity's attribute can serve as a starting point to design representations of references in the communication. They can potentially be reused when designing interlinking provenance and its metadata outside the standardized provenance.

¹³<https://doi.org/10.25495/7gxxk-rd71>

7 Implementation

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The Provenance Management System¹⁴ is a prototype implementation of the FPC Store and Trusted Party components of the architecture presented in Section 3.3. The FPC Store Component supports storage, retrieval, and versioning of finalized provenance components, as well as registration using digital certificates. Optionally, the Trusted Party component can be used to support non-repudiation of origin of finalized provenance components.

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Both components are implemented as web services: a Provenance Management Service and a Trusted Party Service. Both services are designed as RESTful API web applications that communicate over HTTPS. The services are designed to be deployed in multiple instances, each possibly operated by a different organization.

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7.1 Provenance Management Service

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The purpose of the Provenance Management Service is to enable storage and retrieval of finalized provenance components. The Service provides the following features.

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FPC Storage. The Provenance Management Service accepts finalized provenance components as input, which can be serialized into any of the supported formats (PROV-JSON is the preferred format). The input must be digitally signed with a private key, and the signature and a timestamp of the document creation must be provided together with the stored component. The Service performs a series of checks on the provenance component (e.g., validity of the signature using the corresponding certificate stored by the Trusted Party Service, or the uniqueness of identifiers), and if these are successful, the component is stored, and corresponding provenance component metadata (optionally including the extension to support non-repudiation of origin) is generated in the corresponding meta-component. Versioning of a stored provenance component is performed in an analogous way.

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FPC Retrieval. Once a finalized provenance component is stored, users can retrieve it at various granularities: the complete component, just the traversal information, or just the domain-specific part. The component is optionally provided together with its non-repudiation evidence. If only a subset of the component is provided (i.e., a traversal or a domain-specific part), new non-repudiation evidence is generated for that purpose.

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Modes of Operation. The Provenance Management Service supports three modes of operation for different types of usage in the context of the organizational roles defined in the CPF:

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1. **Provenance controller mode.** The organization hosting the Service is a provenance controller. This organization is allowed to store and retrieve components from the storage, whereas all other organizations are allowed only to retrieve components.
2. **Provenance processor mode.** The organization hosting the Service is a provenance processor, but not a controller. The organization does not store its own finalized provenance components. Instead, it stores components on behalf of other organizations.
3. **Combined mode.** The organization hosting the Service is a provenance controller and also a provenance processor for other organizations. As a result, the controller and other organizations may store and retrieve provenance components.

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¹⁴The system was initially developed as part of two master's theses^{32,33} supervised by Rudolf Wittner, the main author of this document. Parts of the text in this section are taken from those theses.

It is up to organizations adopting the framework to determine which mode of operation is most suitable for a given use case or scenario. 772
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7.2 Trusted Party Service 774

The purpose of the Trusted Party Service is to support the trustworthiness of stored finalized provenance components by supporting non-repudiation of origin. The Trusted Party Service is responsible for communicating with the Provenance Management Service and is always assumed to be run by another organization, such as an authority. The Service provides the following features. 775
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Management of client certificates and digital signatures' verification. The Service stores all certificates used to verify digital signatures of components stored in the Provenance Management Service, and checks the signatures on request from the Provenance Management Service. 780
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Issuing non-repudiation evidence. Non-repudiation evidence is issued after successful verification of an FPC signature to provide proof that the signature was valid at the given time. This evidence is stored by the Trusted Party Service and also returned to the Provenance Management Service, where it is stored in a meta-component. This way, users requesting a stored component can receive confirmation from a third party that the digital signature associated with the component was valid. The evidence can also be issued for a subset of a provenance component, which is aligned with the granularity of access control in the Provenance Management Service. 785
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Non-repudiation evidence storage. The Trusted Party Service stores all non-repudiation evidence in case of a potential dispute about the origin of a finalized provenance component. This includes copies of client certificates (and their intermediates), finalized provenance components, and all evidence issued for the components. 794
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7.3 Non-repudiation Policy Evaluation 799

This section summarizes how the CPF and its reference implementation addresses each of the requirements of the non-repudiation policy defined in Section 2.1. 800
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NRO-P1: FPC-controller association. Each finalized provenance component is associated with the corresponding provenance controller by assigning a persistent identifier to that component. The identifier is a URI, the prefix of which uniquely identifies the respective provenance controller. 802
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NRO-P2: Authenticity of FPC. The authenticity of the FPC is achieved by creating a digital signature of the FPC using the provenance processor's private key. This signature is verified by the Trusted Party Service before it is stored. 806
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NRO-P3: Evidence-trusted party association. Non-repudiation evidence is associated with the corresponding trusted party by inclusion of the trusted party's identifier in the evidence. 809
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NRO-P4: Authenticity of evidence. The authenticity of non-repudiation evidence is established by digitally signing the evidence with the trusted party's private key. This signature is verified by the respective provenance controller before the component is stored. 812
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Long-term verifiability of the signature is achieved by long-term storage of the evidence and information required for the verification, and additional protection of private keys. 815
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NRO-P5: Evidence-controller association. Non-repudiation evidence is associated with the corresponding provenance controller by inclusion of the controller's identifier (i.e., FPC identifier) in the evidence. 817
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NRO-P6: FPC generation timestamps. Non-repudiation evidence contains a timestamp indicating when the FPC was generated. 820
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NRO-P7: Evidence generation timestamps. Non-repudiation evidence contains a timestamp indicating when the evidence was generated. 822
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NRO-P8: Trusted timestamps. The timestamp describing the non-repudiation evidence generation is generated by the Trusted Party Service. Instead of generating timestamps locally, the implementation can be extended to generate timestamps by a trusted timestamping authority¹¹. 824
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NRO-P9: Additional timestamps. Additional timestamps required for reconstructing past events can be included in the evidence. 828
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NRO-P10: Self-contained evidence. All data required to verify evidence authenticity is embedded in the evidence. 830
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NRO-P11: Primary evidence storage. Non-repudiation evidence is kept by the respective provenance processor (which may be the same organization as the provenance controller) in the meta-component. 832
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NRO-P12: Independent evidence storage. A copy of non-repudiation evidence is stored by the Trusted Party Service. 835
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NRO-P13: Immutable storage. This requirement can be addressed by using an appropriate storage type for non-repudiation evidence. Three immutable storage types were evaluated for this purpose in our prior work⁴. 837
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NRO-P14: Hardware-backed cryptography. This requirement can be addressed by using an appropriate implementation for cryptographic operations. The use of the PKCS #11 API³⁴, which supports communication with secure hardware such as hardware security modules or smart cards, was simulated as part of our prior work⁴. 840
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NRO-P15: Key compromise reporting window. This requirement must be addressed at the policy level, with a policy adapted for a particular application and legal environment. 844
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8 Provenance Chain Example 846

This section provides an example of a provenance chain documenting a distributed multi-organizational research pipeline from digital pathology. The purpose of this example is to show how the logic defined by the CPM can be applied and its structures used to build up a distributed provenance chain. Finalized provenance components presented in this section support backward traceability and do not support forward traceability. For that reason, no specializations of forward connectors in the traversal information are shown. The example presents the final state of a provenance chain and does not show how the resulting chain 847
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is incrementally constructed. Incremental build of a generic provenance chain including the support for forward traceability is shown in Section 9.

The traversal information – composed of standardized expression of the interconnections and derivations paths – enables traversal and navigation in a distributed provenance chain using a common algorithm regardless of the kind of described activity documented in a particular provenance component. The purpose of the traversal information is not to capture any domain-specific semantic documenting particular described activity, the exclusive purpose is to capture traversal/navigation-related information. The domain-specific semantic is attached to the backbone using a standardized method, which provides further details about the component’s main activity.

The example provided in this Section focuses primarily on finalized provenance components coming from different sources, i.e. the different provenance controllers participating in the considered research process, to build the provenance chain. The example does not prescribe how domain-specific part of finalized provenance components should be expressed and therefore the given representations are used only for illustrative purposes. Domain-specific modeling, in fact, can be highly variable depending on the different purposes for provenance collection that could lead to the recording of different information. The level of detail of captured provenance information depends on the qualified decision of a user of the CPM.

Figures provided in the example use a simplified expression of provenance structures identifiers, meaning that the identifiers are rather descriptive. In reality, fully qualified names composed of a prefix and a local part would be used. The figures also depict the usage of the simplified method for described objects identification. Each of the described activities also contains the `startTime` and `endTime` property. The figures are also simplified in a way so that they do not contain the `cpm:currentAgent` provenance structure related to the main activity. Proper representation all the information can be found in the technical evaluation implementation of the framework.

The presented example considers a research pipeline for digital pathology specialized in the detection of cancer. The pipeline consists of multiple steps, each of which can be carried out by different provenance providers.

The general schema of the resulting provenance chain¹⁵ is depicted in Figure 16. The chain contains five types of finalized provenance components, each documenting a different part of the use case. There may be more “Sample acquisition” and “Sample processing and WSI Generation” bundles in the pipeline. The two “WSI pre-processing” components integrate all the images from the previous steps. The training and testing datasets are then used in the subsequent steps.

¹⁵The same provenance chain structure was used for the evaluation of the CPF.

Figure 16: Overall schema of a provenance chain documenting the running example.

In the following sections, each step of the research pipeline is described, and an application of the CPM (especially the traversal information part) is explained.

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8.1 Biological sample acquisition

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As the first step, a tissue specimen is collected from a patient during a clinical intervention – breast biopsy – and sent to pathology for examination. Finalized provenance component describing the acquisition of a sample is depicted in Figure 17.

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Figure 17: Provenance component documenting sample acquisition.

This provenance component represents the beginning of the chain, so the traversal information does not contain a backward connector nor a sender agent. The start of the chain is expressed as a main activity, which generates a PROV entity – forward connector – representing the acquired sample that will be sent to the next organization for the following step.

If there was a previous step documenting the sample source according to the CPM specifications – e.g., a finalized provenance component documenting patient related clinical data using HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources standard (FHIR) – this would be linked using the backward connector and the sender agent provenance structures.

8.2 Sample processing and image generation

In this part of the research pipeline, the Pathology Laboratory receives the sample, prepares it for a consecutive analysis, performs the diagnostics, and generates image data out of the samples. After having passed an initial quality check and being registered in the Laboratory Information System, a sequence of laboratory procedures is put in place to produce a collection of glass slides for the case (i.e., a patient). First, the tissue sample is reduced to smaller fragments and placed into labeled bio-cassettes ready for washing cycles and inclusion in paraffin block (Formalin-Fixed Paraffin-Embedded, FFPE). Once cooled, the resulting paraffin block is cut into thin slices which are bathed, placed on a labeled glass slide and finally dried for some time depending on the specific glass preparation protocol. Tissue slices are then stained to enhance the different cellular structures and covered with a coverslip. After a few hours of drying the glass slides are ready to be analyzed, scanned, and annotated for the purpose of training and validation of machine learning models.

Finalized provenance component describing the preparation of a glass slide is depicted in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Provenance component documenting glass slides preparation. The figure is simplified in a way that each sample can be split into multiple blocks, and each block can be split into multiple slices that are put on a glass. All the consecutive activities are then carried out for each glass individually. As a result, the main activity generates multiple WSI connectors, each for a different image generated from a different glass slide.

testing is used to assess the quality of the model at regular intervals. Testing is also used to determine whether any hyperparameters (parameters of the learning algorithm) need to be adjusted. The results of this step are two trained models – the models with the best accuracy and the last model of the training iterations. This is depicted in Figure 20.

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Figure 20: Finalized provenance component documenting machine learning model training. The figure is simplified in a way that there may be more iterations of the AI model training executed, so there may be more intermediate AI models trained. In reality, there are two training datasets – one with positive cases, and one with negative cases. These are distinguished by the algorithm using the WSIs filename convention used by the group (see the implementation for further details).

In this example, the training dataset is coming from the same previous step, which is expressed using a single backward connector and a sender agent.

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8.5 AI Model Evaluation

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During the evaluation, the trained model is applied to the validation dataset generated in the preprocessing step (Step 3) to let the trained model infer the presence of carcinoma cells in the unseen images. The results are evaluation using both automated metrics as well as manual inspection by an experienced pathologist. This step is done to assess the overall performance of the pipeline. Respective provenance component is depicted in Figure 21.

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Presume¹⁶ that this is the last step of the research pipeline, because the metrics itself would not be expected to be used by further organizations, the provenance component does not contain any forward connectors.

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¹⁶In reality, the metrics could be used by a potential user of the trained model.

Figure 21: Finalized provenance component documenting machine learning model evaluation. The figure is simplified in a way that there are more heatmaps generated as the output of the reporting process.

9 Provenance Chain Operations Examples

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This section show examples of how a provenance chain can be incrementally built including examples of respective meta-components content to demonstrate the usage of the versioning mechanism defined in the CPF.

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A provenance chain is formed by finalized provenance components, which can be added to the chain by two types of operations with respect to an existing component.

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- Adding a subsequent component;
- Adding a preceding component.

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The examples presented in this section demonstrate the application of these two types of operations, starting with simple examples and then advancing to more complex situations as follows:

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- Adding a subsequent provenance component with forward traceability;
- Adding a preceding provenance component with forward traceability;
- Adding a subsequent provenance component with redundant connectors without forward traceability;
- Adding a subsequent provenance with redundant connectors with forward traceability;
- Forking a provenance component by adding a subsequent or preceding provenance component with redundant connectors with forward traceability;

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To support the readability and understandability of the presented figures, some of the figures are simplified in a way that they do not present some technical details which are not necessary to understand the presented concept. The simplification includes:

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- Omitting the domain-specific part of provenance components. The domain-specific information part is not relevant for linking provenance components.
- Omitting explicit statements about the types of the relations between respective provenance structures. Types of the relations are defined in the CPM.
- Omitting identifiers and attributes of provenance components' main activity.
- Omitting mandatory agents in the traversal information.
- Omitting some mandatory/optional attributes of the connectors (if these are not related to linking provenance components in a provenance chain).
- Omitting derivations between connectors (if not present, they are assumed implicitly).
- Omitting the non-latest versions of a provenance component. The provenance components in the presented examples are updated according to the CPM. After the update, the original version of the updated provenance component is not shown. How the versions are expressed in meta-component is shown.
- Omitting the forward connectors in the last component of a provenance chain in case it is not used in particular example.
- All provenance components have associated a common shared meta-component. In practice, each provenance component can have associated its own meta-component.
- Omitting namespaces of provenance structure identifiers.

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9.1 Adding a subsequent provenance component

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This section describes the procedure which adds a subsequent provenance component to an existing provenance chain.

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A forward connector in an existing provenance component serves to connect additional provenance components without any modification of the existing component. This is realized by including the identifier of the forward connector in the newly connected component, which essentially creates a backward link between the two components (Figure 22).

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Figure 22: Backward link between two provenance components.

Respective meta-component's state is depicted in Figure 23.

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Figure 23: State of the corresponding meta-component.

The process can be iterated to add unlimited number of subsequent components to the chain (either after the bundle `Bundle_a_v1` or after the bundle `Bundle_B_v1`). Optionally, a forward link from the `Bundle_A_v1` to the `Bundle_B_v1` can be created. As the initial finalized provenance component can not be modified directly due to the its immutability property, its new version with the forward link is created (Figure 24).

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Figure 24: Creation of a forward link.

Respective meta-component's state is depicted in Figure 25.

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Figure 25: State of the corresponding meta-component.

9.2 Adding a preceding provenance component

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This section describes the procedure which adds a preceding provenance component to an existing provenance chain. This might be useful especially in legacy use cases for which provenance chains are constructed retrospectively. In such scenarios, the order of provenance components finalization does not necessarily follow their order in the resulting chain.

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First, assume the existence of a provenance chain (Figure 26).

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A new provenance component that is going to be linked with the existing component is created. At this point, there are two independent provenance components (Figure 27).

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Figure 26: Initial state of a provenance chain. The presented existing component does not include any backward connectors. In general, the component can contain backward connectors, but these would be not used to add a preceding component to the chain, as the addition of a new backward connector is the goal of this example.

Figure 27: Creation of a new provenance component to be linked.

Respective meta-component content is depicted in Figure 28.

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Figure 28: State of the corresponding meta-component.

At this point, the two independent provenance components can be linked. This is only possible when someone (not necessarily a provenance controller/processor) initiates the linkage. The structure of the traversal information included in the resulting linked provenance components is then dependent on the order of operations, which is affected by which link, either forward or backward link, is created first. Indeed, different options may better fit different scenarios. For instance, consider an open repository with a publicly available dataset which has already been provided and used by users. At this point, the users have already created their provenance component, and the provenance component of the repository is going to be built retrospectively (so we are adding the preceding provenance component to the chain). As the repository is open, presume that the repository provider does not necessarily know who the receivers are. In such a scenario, it may be more feasible that once the receivers learn about the existence of the preceding provenance component (including all the necessary information to create the link), they create the backward links first and they notify the sender to create the forward links. On the other hand, when a biobank provides samples to organizations, the biobank typically tracks the receivers of the samples. In such a scenario, the biobank may create a provenance component with the forward link first and then notify the receivers to create the backward links.

Presume that the backward link is created first (Figure 29), so that the receiver creates a new version of the provenance component with a link to the sender's component. Respective meta-component content is depicted in Figure 30.

Figure 29: Creating a subsequent provenance component.

Figure 30: State of the corresponding meta-component.

Optionally, a forward link from the Bundle_C_v1 to the Bundle_D_v1 can be created if necessary, information is provided to the receiver (Figure 31). Respective meta-component content is depicted in Figure 32.

Figure 31: Creating a forward link.

Figure 32: State of the corresponding meta-component.

Alternatively, the forward link can also be created immediately before creating the backward link in cases when all the necessary information is already known to the receiver (so that there would be just a single version of the `Bundle_C`). The other option is that the sender is notified about the existence of the component before the receiver, so that the forward link is created before the backward link (the biobank's example). Similarly, depending on what information is available to the sender at the moment of the component creation, there could be two versions of the provenance component (without the forward link and another one with the forward link added) or a single version (with the forward link already included).

9.3 Adding a subsequent provenance component with redundant connectors without forward traceability

This section describes a procedure which adds subsequent provenance components to an existing provenance chain with the support of redundant connectors for backward traceability. Meta-component is not provided here, as it just simply follows the examples of meta-component as already shown in the previous examples.

Assume a provenance chain that consists of two provenance components (Figure 33). Assume that each forward connector present in the example is derived from all backward connectors in the provenance components (the derivations are omitted in figures for better readability).

Figure 33: A provenance chain consisting of two provenance components.

To add a subsequent provenance component to the end of the chain (after `z:bundle1`), the following procedure is applied:

1. Add a subsequent provenance component to the chain by applying the procedure for “Adding a subsequent provenance component”.
2. Duplicate all the backward connectors (with respective derivations) from the component in the “original” end of the chain (`z:bundle1`) that are used as a source of derivation between the forward connector used to connect the new component into the newly added component (the derivation is there by presumption stated in the beginning of this subsection).
3. Do not duplicate any other backward connector (this is not shown in this example).

By applying the procedure on the assumed provenance chain, the following chain is obtained (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Adding a provenance component with redundant backward connectors. The green box shows how the backward connectors from the original bundle are duplicated in the newly added component to show the redundant link to the component `y:bundle1`.

To add a subsequent provenance component to the end of the chain (after `a:bundle1`) with redundant connectors, the described procedure is generalized:

1. Add a subsequent provenance component to the chain by applying the procedure for “Adding a subsequent provenance component”.
2. Duplicate the whole derivation chain of all the backward connectors from the the component in the chain (`z:bundle1` or `a:bundle1` depending on where the subsequent component will be added) that are used as a source of derivation between the forward connector used to connect the new component in the newly added component (it is there by presumption stated in the beginning of this subsection).
3. Do not duplicate any other connectors.

Application of the generalized procedure (either for adding a new component after the component `a:bundle1` and after the component `z:bundle1`) is presented in Figure 35. The green box shows how the backward connectors from the original bundle are duplicated in the newly added component.

Figure 35: Adding provenance components with redundant backward connectors. The blue box shows how the derivation chain of the respective backward connectors from the original bundle are duplicated in the newly added component. Similarly to the previous step, the green box shows how the backward connectors from the original bundle are duplicated in the newly added component.

Now, if the component `z:bundle1` disappears for some reason, the respective links to the bundle `z:bundle1` becomes invalid, however, the redundant links can be used to access the component `y:bundle1` from respective provenance components (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Provenance component `z:bundle1` disappears. The red color indicates the invalidity of the connectors that linked to the disappeared component.

9.4 Adding a subsequent provenance component with redundant connectors with forward traceability

This section describes a procedure which adds subsequent/preceding provenance components to an existing provenance chain with the support of redundant connectors for backward and forward traceability. Assume that each forward connector present in the example is derived from all backward connectors in provenance component (the derivations are omitted in figures for better readability). Assume a provenance chain that consists of two provenance components linked in both directions (Figure 37).

Figure 37: Initial state of a provenance chain.

Respective meta-component content is shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38: State of the corresponding meta-component.

Another component can be added to the chain using the mechanism for “Adding a subsequent provenance component with redundant connectors without forward traceability” (Figure 39). 1098
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Figure 39: Adding a provenance component with redundant backward connectors. The green box shows how the backward connectors from the original bundle are duplicated in the newly added component to show the redundant link.

Respective meta-component content is depicted in Figure 40.

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Figure 40: State of the corresponding meta-component.

The “middle” component of the chain is now updated to create the forward link to the newly added component. This is realized by applying the mechanism for “Adding a subsequent provenance component” to the connector used by the main activity in the newly added component (Figure 41).

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Figure 41: Creating a forward link, the red box shows the “local change” to create the forward link.

Respective meta-component content is depicted in Figure 42.

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Figure 42: State of the corresponding meta-component.

As the respective provenance processor in the middle of the chain now has the information about the new component (a:bundle1), the information can be propagated by to other provenance components linked to the “middle” provenance component (y:bundle1v2 in this step) (Figure 43).

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Figure 43: Propagating the information about the forward link to create the redundant forward links. The blue box highlights how the existing forward link in component z:bundle1v2 is propagated to create the redundant link in component y:bundle1v3.

Respective meta-component content is depicted in Figure 44.

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Figure 44: State of the corresponding meta-component.

The whole procedure can be repeated to add another subsequent component to the chain (Figure 45). The links between components are omitted for readability.

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Meta-component would be updated analogously to the presented meta-components examples – the “revision chain” between respective provenance components would be prolonged where necessary.

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Figure 45: Adding another subsequent provenance component to the provenance chain. The blue boxes show the propagation of respective forward link. The green boxes show the propagation of the backward link.

9.5 Forking a provenance component by adding a subsequent or preceding provenance component with redundant connectors with forward traceability

The whole procedure can be repeated to add another subsequent component to the chain in “non-linear” way. This may happen, for instance, in a situation when the component `z:bundle1v3` from the previous example (Figure 45) would represent a dataset deposited in a public repository that has already been used by another organization which generated a provenance component. The “non-linear” component then represent a new organization using the dataset with generated provenance component (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Adding a “non-linear” provenance component to a provenance chain. The red box depicts the local change in component `z:bundle1v3` to create a forward link to the new component. The blue box shows how the forward link is propagated to another provenance component to create a redundant forward link. The blue and red arrows show the new links. The other links between provenance components are omitted for readability.

Similarly, the mechanism for “Adding a preceding provenance component” can be used to add a “non-linear” provenance component. Figure 47 depicts how a new preceding component `d:bundle1` is added before the component `a:bundle1v2`. The redundant forward connectors are created analogously to the previous steps.

Figure 47: Adding a preceding “non-linear” provenance component. The red box depicts a local change to create a backward link to the new provenance component. The green box shows how the backward link is propagated. The blue box shows how the forward link from the newly added component is propagated. The arrows between the components are used to depict the order of the components of the chain. The actual links between the components are omitted for simplicity.

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